

Searches for resonances decaying to pairs of heavy bosons in ATLAS

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Many new physics models predict the existence of Higgs-like particles decaying into two bosons (W , Z , photon, or Higgs boson) making these important signatures in the search for new physics. Searches for $V\gamma$, VV , and VH (with $V = W$ or Z) resonances have been performed in various final states. In some of these searches, jet substructure techniques are used to disentangle the hadronic decay products in highly boosted configurations. This paper summarizes recent ATLAS searches with Run 2 data collected at the LHC and explains the experimental methods used, including vector-boson and Higgs-boson tagging techniques.

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Introduction

Several theories extending the Standard Model (SM) predict the existence of heavy resonances X that decay into pairs of bosons: $X \rightarrow VV'$ or $X \rightarrow VH$, where $V^{(\prime)}$ can be either a Z or a W boson or a γ . The existence of new resonances could be discovered by the experiments at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC), such as ATLAS, through the observation of a local excess in a smoothly falling mass spectrum, which makes this search relatively model-independent.

Among the different Beyond Standard Model theories, the following ones can be studied through VV analyses: *warped extra dimensions*, which introduces new particles called *Radion* (with spin 0) and *RSG (Randall-Sudrum graviton)*, with spin 2); the *Georgi-Machacek theory (GM)*, which introduces a *singly-charged Higgs boson (H_5^\pm)*; the *Heavy Vector Triplet (HVT)*, a framework used as a simplified approach which assumes the existence of new Z' and W' bosons.

These new resonances can be produced through *gluon-gluon fusion (ggF)*, described by the Feynman diagram on the left in figure 1, *quark-antiquark annihilation (qqA)*, where the two gluons of the previous diagram are replaced by a quark and an antiquark, and *vector boson fusion (VBF)*, described by the Feynman diagram on the right in figure 1.

Figure 1: Two possible production modes of new resonances: gluon-gluon fusion (ggF) on the left and vector boson fusion (VBF) on the right.

According to the decay mode of the V bosons three different final states can be identified, with l being an electron or a muon: fully-hadronic ($VV \rightarrow qq\bar{q}\bar{q}$), semileptonic ($VV \rightarrow qqll$, $VV \rightarrow qq\nu\nu$, $VV \rightarrow qq\bar{l}\nu$) and fully-leptonic ($VV \rightarrow ll\bar{l}\bar{l}$, $VV \rightarrow \nu\nu\nu\nu$, $VV \rightarrow l\nu\bar{l}\nu$, $VV \rightarrow l\nu\bar{l}\nu$).

Final states containing hadrons can be observed in two different regimes: *merged*, where large-radius jets are used to identify a vector boson decaying to quarks, and *resolved*, where two small-radius jets from the V decay can be distinguished. The first regime is dominant at high mass of the resonance X (m_X) and high p_T , while the second one is important in the low and intermediate m_X range, as shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Schematic illustration of the two regimes (resolved and merged) in which final states containing hadrons can be observed.

Reconstruction and analysis steps

After the reconstruction and identification of physical objects in the event, an important step in the search for heavy resonances is the classification into ggF and VBF categories. For this purpose, the first VV analyses [1, 2] performed by the ATLAS Collaboration [3] exploited the fact that VBF processes have two additional jets in the final state with respect to ggF processes, as shown in figure 1. These two jets, called *VBF-tag jets*, are kinematically different from those originated by the hadronic decay of V bosons, being well separated in pseudorapidity and having large dijet invariant mass. This approach, however, required the reconstruction of both VBF-tag jets; therefore the number of events classified as ggF or VBF was affected by the jets reconstruction efficiency. A more recent analysis [4] introduced the use of a *Recurrent Neural Network* (RNN) for the ggF/VBF categorization. This RNN uses the four-momenta of small-radius jets as input and allows the recovery of $\sim 30\%$ more signal events than the previous approach, without requiring the reconstruction of both VBF-tag jets. The distribution of the RNN output, called *score*, depends on the assumed model of a heavy resonance, its mass and decay mode. The comparison between the RNN score of simulated ggF and VBF events produced by different new resonances (Radion, W' and graviton) of mass 1 TeV is shown in figure 3. An event is classified as VBF (ggF) if its RNN score is above (below) 0.8, where the threshold is chosen in order to maximise the sensitivity to VBF signals.

Figure 3: Output (score) of the RNN used to classify events between VBF and ggF categories [4].

The use of the RNN yields a relative increase in the efficiency of VBF categorization from 10% (5%) at 0.5 TeV to 60% (50%) at 3 TeV for a scalar resonance (spin-1 or spin-2 resonance) compared to the previous selection [1, 2], with similar background rejections [4].

A challenge for analyses focusing on final states containing hadrons is the rejection of QCD jets; in the semileptonic channel the production of these jets in association with a W/Z boson according to the V +jets processes is the dominant source of background. The *boson tagger* [5] is used to reject these background jets.

The fully-hadronic analysis used for the first time a boson tagger exploiting *Track-CaloClusters* (TCC) jets, reconstructed using both tracking and calorimeter information. A dedicated optimisation of this TCC-based tagger has been done for the semileptonic analysis; it is based on a simultaneous cut on the jet mass and the correlation substructure variable $D2$ [6]. The boson tagger used for the semileptonic channel has been also calibrated with real data; in particular, scale factors have been derived using data and simulated $t\bar{t}$ events.

Recent results

A fit of the signal plus background hypothesis can be performed for probing the production of the heavy resonance, with its production cross-section in the VV decay mode, $\sigma(pp \rightarrow X \rightarrow VV)$, as the parameter of interest.

Upper limits on production cross-sections can be computed in each of the three channels (fully-hadronic, semileptonic, fully-leptonic), eventually combining different possible final states (e.g., the semileptonic channel contributions from final states with 0, 1 and 2 charged leptons are combined). The limits at 95% Confidence Level (CL) for the production of a W' and a graviton are shown in figure 4, on the left and on the right respectively. By combining the contributions from the three different channels, each of which is sensitive in a different mass range, it is possible to derive limits from 300 GeV up to 5 TeV.

Figure 4: Limits at 95% CL on the production cross-section of a W' (left) and a graviton (right) [7].

The results shown in the fully-leptonic channel have recently been updated using the entire dataset collected by the ATLAS experiment between 2015 and 2018 (LHC Run 2), corresponding to a total integrated luminosity of 139 fb^{-1} [8]. The production of a singly-charged Higgs boson of the GM model and of a W' boson is investigated in this analysis. Exclusion limits at 95% CL on the production cross-section times branching ratio can be derived. Results for W' and the charged GM Higgs boson are shown in figure 5, on the left and on the right respectively.

Values of the W' mass below 2.4 TeV and 2.5 TeV can be excluded for two different models (model A [9] predicts new weakly coupled vector resonances with comparable branching ratios to fermions and gauge bosons, while model B [10] is representative of a HVT produced in a strongly-coupled scenario with suppressed fermionic couplings). For H_5^\pm a local excess of events above the SM expectations at a resonance mass of ~ 375 GeV can be observed, with a 2.8 standard deviation significance. It can therefore be concluded that no significant deviation from the SM has been observed for neither of the two resonances.

Figure 5: Limits at 95% CL on the production cross-section times branching ratio of W' (left) and H_5^\pm (right) in the fully-leptonic channel with 139 fb^{-1} [8].

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